

Letras Raras Journal, Academic Journal of Language and Literature, v. 14, Special Issue. 2025

Editorial

The *Letras Raras Journal*, an academic publication devoted to Linguistics and Literature and affiliated with the Laboratory for Studies in Letters and Languages in Contemporary Times (Universidade Federal de Campina Grande), is pleased to present its 2025 special issue, which stems from the IV Meeting of the Prosody Seminar, held at the Universidade Federal da Paraíba on April 24th, 25th, and 26th, 2024.

This volume brings together a robust collection of articles that reflect the vitality and diversity of research in prosody and intonation, exploring their multifaceted interfaces with areas such as language acquisition, second language learning, language contact, the description of national indigenous languages, dialectology, phonetics, phonology, pragmatics, processing, sociolinguistics, syntax, and discourse. The thematic and methodological plurality of the contributions highlights the dynamism of the field and the researchers' commitment to both theoretical advancement and practical application in prosodic studies.

Organized by Professors Carolina Gomes da Silva (UFPB) and Manuella Carnaval (UFRJ), this dossier features contributions from scholars affiliated with Brazilian and Latin American institutions, including Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Universidade Federal Fluminense, Universidade Federal da Paraíba, Universidade Federal da Integração Latino-americana, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México and Universidad Autónoma de Querétaro. This institutional diversity underscores the collaborative and transnational nature of the event that inspired this edition.

Beyond documenting the academic discussions held during the seminar, this publication aims to broaden the reach of the reflections presented, fostering the exchange of knowledge and encouraging new investigations into prosodic phenomena across varied contexts. The articles compiled here offer readers a compelling overview of current research, revealing both conceptual advances and methodological challenges that shape the field.

Revista Letras Raras

ISSN: 2317-2347 – v. 14, Special Issue – e6235 (2025)

Todo o conteúdo da RLR está licenciado sob Creative Commons Atribuição 4.0 Internacional

We invite you, dear reader, to engage with this special issue with attentiveness and curiosity. May the readings herein inspire new questions, stimulate collaborations, and contribute to the strengthening of linguistic research in its many dimensions. Access the texts, share them with your academic network, and take part in building a science that is increasingly connected, critical, and plural.

Enjoy your reading!

Maria Rennally Soares da Silva, Federal University of Paraíba, Brazil

Josilene Pinheiro-Mariz, Federal University of Campina Grande, Brazil

Editors of *Letras Raras Journal* –Academic Journal of the LELLC Research Group / Laboratory of Contemporary Language and Literature Studies / Federal University of Campina Grande.